

doi 10.5281/zenodo.10648842

Vol. 06 Issue 11 Nov - 2023

Manuscript ID: #01106

COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION IN IMPLEMENTATION SOCIAL FORESTRY PROGRAM IN THE UPTD KPHP SANTAN AREA, EAST KALIMANTAN PROVINCE

Study Case in Bhuana Jaya Village in the UPTD KPHP Santan Area East Kalimantan Province

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ABSTRACT

In efforts to realize the concept of sustainable forest management, it is necessary to involve communities around the forest as the main actors who often interact with the forest. The Social Forestry Program aims to increase community participation in managing forests so that their standard of living can be improved and forest sustainability maintained. The research aims to determine the level of participation of the Bhuana Jaya Village Community in the Implementation of the Social Forestry Program in the UPTD KPHP Santan Area. The research was carried out from March 2022 to April 2022 in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District. Data was obtained directly through direct observation and interviews with 15 members of the Forest Farmers Group who obtained Social Forestry permits and managed Community Forests in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District. The data collected was processed and clarified according to the research objectives and then analyzed using qualitative data analysis. The research results show that the level of community participation in implementing the Social Forestry program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District is very high with an average score of 2.78.

KEYWORDS:

Community Participation, Social Forestry Program, East Kalimantan.

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INTRODUCTION

Social Forestry is a sustainable forest management system carried out in state forest areas or private/customary forests implemented by local communities or customary law communities as the main treatment to improve their welfare, environmental balance, and socio-cultural dynamics in the form of Village Forests, Community Forests, and Forests. Community Crops, Community Forests, Customary Forests and Forestry Partnerships [1].

Social forestry is a sustainable forest management system implemented in state forest areas or private/customary forests implemented by local communities or customary law communities as the main actors to improve their welfare, environmental balance, and socio-cultural dynamics in the form of Village Forests, Community Forests, Plantation Forests People, Community Forests, Customary Forests, and Forestry Partnerships [2].

The Social Forestry Program itself aims to improve community welfare through empowerment patterns while still being guided by sustainability aspects. The Social Forestry Program will open up opportunities for communities around forests to apply for forest area management rights to the government. The Social Forestry Program is also expected to contribute to solving the nation's problems in the aspect of justice, reducing the gap between villages and cities, resolving tenure conflicts, increasing food and climate security, and realizing sustainable forest management [3].

Local community participation in forest management is an important aspect of sustainable development[4]. That various ways of community-based management, such as self-organizing, institutional development, experimentation, knowledge elaboration, and social learning can make unsustainable practices more sustainable [5]. Therefore, Social Forestry can be interpreted as an approach taken to mitigate increasing deforestation and forest degradation and overcome the negative impacts of local community activities in forests by involving communities as subjects in forest management [6].Community participation is also to preserve existing forests because it can be said that the key to success in preventing and dealing with damage to existing forests is determined by the size of community participation.

Bhuana Jaya Village was originally a transmigration location that was opened in 1981 and at that time was still a forest. The majority of residents living in Bhuana Jaya Village have socio-cultural backgrounds from various ethnicities, the majority of the population's livelihood is rice farming. Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village is a pattern of Social Forestry in the form of Community Forestry (HKm) whose main use is aimed at community empowerment.

The research aims to determine the level of participation of the Bhuana Jaya Village Community in the Implementation of the Social Forestry Program in the UPTD KPHP Santan Area.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Place and Time of Research

The place of research was carried out in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District. The research was conducted from March 2022 to April 2022.

B. Materials and Tools

The materials and tools used are a camera, voice recorder, and interview guide sheet.

C. Data Collection Methods

The data collection methods used in this research were observation and interviews with the community.

D. Population

The population that was the object of this research were 15 members of the Forest Farmer Group who obtained a Social Forestry permit and managed Community Forests in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District.

E. Data Collection

The data collected were: (1) primary in the form of interviews with the people of Bhuana Jaya Village who are members of forest farmer groups and have Social Forestry permits; and (2) secondary data in the form of activity results reports and others.

F. Data Analysis

The data obtained through observations and interviews are described qualitatively, namely by examining all the data obtained classifying them based on their categories, and then looking for relationships with other categories to illustrate the level of community participation in the implementation of the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District. Data analysis uses Likert Scale measurements. For attitude analysis, the Likert Scale is based on data classification, namely attitude scales, scores, and categories. According to [7], the Likert Scale is a tool for measuring attitudes from very positive to very negative levels, to show the extent of agreement or disagreement with the statements proposed by the researcher. This Likert Scale is also called the Summated Ratings Method, by using the Summated Ratings Method you will find scores on the Likert Scale measurement, namely giving the highest and lowest scores for each answer to the question asked to the respondent. In this research, the highest answer score for a question will be determined, namely 3, while the lowest answer score is 1. For the question scale, those who answered strongly yes were given a value of 3, sometimes they were given a value of 2, and those who answered no were given a value of 1.

To get a ranking of participation of forest farmer group members, the total score is a maximum of 3 and a minimum of 1. Next, the scores for each respondent are added up and a ranking is made using the following rating scale:

Difference per category = {Highest Score -Lowest Score} : {Number of Categories}

Difference per category = (3 – 1) : (3) = 0,67.

Based on the formula above, you can see the level of each value in Table 2.

Table 2. Level of Community Participation

Number	Level of Community Participation	
	Level	Category
1	Very High	2,35 – 3,00
2	Till	1,68 – 2,35
3	Low	1,00 – 1,67

Source: Modified Likert Scale Results

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. General description of Bhuana Jaya Village

Bhuana Jaya Village was originally a transmigration location that was opened in 1981 and at that time was still a forest. the majority of residents living in Bhuana Jaya Village have socio-cultural backgrounds from various ethnicities or tribes such as Javanese (70%); Sundanese (20%); residents such as Dayak, Kutai, and Banjar (9%); and others such as the Bugis ethnic group (1%). Based on the Governor's Decree (Eri Suparjan) in 1981, the total area of Bhuana Jaya Village is 4,957 Ha which is directly adjacent to Mulawarman and Sukamaju Villages to the north, Bukit Pariaman Village to the east and south, and Separi Village to the west with the majority of its residents' livelihoods is a rice farmer.

B. General Description of KPHP Coconut Milk

KPHP Santan as one of the KPHs managed by East Kalimantan Province is located between 116°47'16.8" East Longitude - 117°27'10.8" East Longitude and between 0°36'50.4" N - 0°19'33.6" South Latitude. Administratively, the government is located in 3 Regency/City government administration areas from 9 Regency areas in East Kalimantan, namely: Kutai Kartanegara Regency, East Kutai Regency, and Bontang City.

The area of the KPHP Santan Area is based on the Determination of the KPHL and KPHP Areas of East Kalimantan Province Number: SK.674/Menhut-II/2011, December 1, 2011, namely an area of 270,557 Ha. Then adjusted to the Decree of the Minister of Forestry Number: SK. 718/Menhut-II/2014 concerning Forest Areas of East Kalimantan Province and North Kalimantan Province and a map of boundary development by BPKH region IV Samarinda, so that the area of the Santan KPHP is 267,068 Ha.

The spatial distribution of the KPHP Santan management area is based on the main forest function, namely in the Production Forest (HP) area, which in total reaches 8% of the total Production Forest (HP) in East Kalimantan Province. Apart from the Production Forest, the management area is also in the Protected Forest (HL) area, reaching an area of 1.2% of the total existing Protected Forest. The Santan KPHP is located in approximately 3.2% of the forest area in East Kalimantan Province. Furthermore, in terms of forest functions, most of the KPHP Santan management area is located in Production Forests. The majority (90.9%) of the KPHP Santan management area consists of forest areas with flat and sloping topographic conditions. Most of the KPHP Santan area is a Timber Estate area.

C. General Description of Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village

Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village is a pattern of Social Forestry in the form of Community Forestry (HKm) whose main use is aimed at community empowerment.

In its licensing, Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village has forest management covering an area of 22 Ha in the Production Forest area and is given to the community as the Buah Himba Forest Farmers Group (KTH) in Bhuana Jaya Village. The number of members of the Buah Himba forest farmer group is 15 people, consisting of 13 men and 2 women. Community Forest management approval is given to forest farmer groups for 35 years and is evaluated every 5 years.

Approval for forest management in the KTH Buah Himba Community Forest Social Forestry program in Bhuana Jaya Village includes area utilization, environmental services utilization, non-timber forest product (NTFP) collection utilization, and timber forest product collection utilization. Community Forest management approval does not constitute an ownership right to a forest area, and communities who obtain a management permit are obliged to carry out Forest management by the principles of Sustainable Forest Management, protect their area from environmental pollution, mark

the boundaries of their work area, prepare a Forest management work plan, and submit implementation report to KPHP Santan. Furthermore, Forest Farmer Groups have the right to plant and maintain forests in their work areas, then organize forest products, pay non-tax state revenues from the results of Social Forestry activities, as well as maintain the function of the Forest, and carry out safeguards for the protection of the Forests they manage.

D. Community Participation in Social Forestry

Community participation in implementing the Social Forestry program in Bhuana Jaya Village is divided into two parts, namely:

1. Community Participation in Planning, Training, and Development of Forest Farmer Groups

Participation in planning, training, and development of forest farmer groups includes community participation in meetings to prepare work plans for social forestry businesses, community participation in the distribution of work plots, and community participation in the training and development of forest farmer groups.

a. Community Participation in Meetings for Preparing Social Forestry Business Work Plans

The meeting to prepare the Social Forestry Business Work Plan (RKUPS) is one of the planning activities to develop forest management activities in implementing the Social Forestry program. Community Participation in the Meeting for Preparing the Social Forestry Business Work Plan (RKUPS) is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Community Participation in the Meeting for Preparing Social Forestry Business Work Plans (RKUPS) in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	6	3	18
2	Sometimes	9	2	18
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		36
Average				2,40

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 1, 6 respondents often take part in social forestry business work plan meetings and 9 respondents sometimes take part in social forestry business work plan meetings. The total score obtained was 36 scores with an average score of 2.40 in the very high category.

The Social Forestry business work plan meeting was held to prepare a business work plan for the implementation of the Social Forestry program in the form of preparing activity plans for dividing plots for area management, planting, maintenance, utilization of environmental services, utilization of non-timber forest products, and safeguarding forest and land fire prevention in implementing the program Social Forestry.

b. Community Participation in the Distribution of Work Plots

Division of work plots is the division of the forest area into work plots which will be managed by each member. Community participation in the distribution of work plots can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Community Participation in the Distribution of Work Plots in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	14	3	42
2	Sometimes	1	2	2
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		44
Average				2,93

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 2, it is known that 14 respondents often participate in work plot distribution activities because they consider this activity important, and 1 respondent sometimes participates because there are many other activities. The total score obtained was 44 scores with an average score of 2.93 in the very high category.

The division of forest areas in the implementation of the Social Forestry program into working plots is carried out to determine the plots that will be managed by each member of the farmer group so that management activities are more efficient.

c. Community Participation in Training and Development

Training and development of forest farmer groups is carried out to increase community skills, abilities, and experience in managing and utilizing forests. Community participation in training and development can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Community Participation in Training and Development in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	15	3	45
2	Sometimes	0	2	0
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		45
Average				3,00

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 3, all respondents often participate in training and development activities for forest farmer groups. The total score obtained was 45 scores with an average score of 3.00 in the very high category.

The training and development that has been carried out at the Buah Himba Forest Farmer Group in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District is training on the use of non-wood forest products for Kelulut honey bees and compost making.

d. Recapitulation of Community Participation in Planning, Training, and Development of Forest Farmer Groups

A recapitulation of community participation in planning, training, and development of forest farming groups is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Recapitulation of Community Participation in Planning, Training, and Development of Forest Farmer Groups in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

Questionnaire	Y / S (3)	NS	KK (2)	NS	T (1)	NS	Total Score	Average Score
Drafting RKUPS	6	18	9	18	-	-	36	2,40
Division of Work Plots	14	42	1	2	-	-	44	2,93
Training and development	15	45	-	-	-	-	45	3,00
Amount								8,33
Category								2,78

Based on Table 4, shows that community participation in the Planning, Training, and Development of Forest Farmer Groups in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District, the average scale score of 2.78 is in the very high category.

2. Participation in Implementation

Participation in implementing the Social Forestry program includes participation in planting, participation in maintenance, participation in the utilization of environmental services, participation in the utilization of non-timber forest products, and participation in securing and preventing forest and land fires.

a. Community Participation in Planting

Community participation in planting forestry plant seeds and fruit in the forest area of Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Community Participation in Planting Forestry Plant Seeds and Fruits in the Bhuana Jaya Village Forest Area, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	15	3	45
2	Sometimes	0	2	0
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		45
Average				3,00

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 5, it is known that all respondents often participate in planting because they consider planting to be the most important thing to do. The total score obtained was 45 with an average score of 3.00 in the very high category.

In this planting activity, the seeds planted are forestry plant seeds and fruit plant seeds such as lai plant seeds and gaharu plant seeds, while the type of fruit plant seeds is durian plant seeds.

b. Community Participation in Maintenance

Maintenance is an activity carried out to maintain and protect plants from pests and plant diseases by carrying out watering, spraying, fertilizing, and so on. Community participation in maintenance can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Community Participation in Maintaining Forestry Plant Seeds and Fruits in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggaraong Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	13	3	39
2	Sometimes	2	2	4
3	Never	1	1	0
Total		15		43
Average				2,87

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 6, it is known that 13 respondents often participate in maintenance because many plants die and 2 respondents sometimes participate in maintenance because they have other work. The total score obtained was 43 with an average score of 2.87 in the very high category

c. Participation in the Utilization of Environmental Services

Community participation in utilizing environmental services in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggaraong Seberang District can be seen in Table 7.

Table 7. Community Participation in Utilizing Environmental Services in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggaraong Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	12	3	36
2	Sometimes	2	2	4
3	Never	1	1	1
Total		15		41
Average				2,73

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 7, it is known that 12 respondents often participate in the utilization of environmental services 2 respondents sometimes participate in the utilization of environmental services and 1 respondent never participates in environmental service utilization activities. The total score obtained was 41 with an average score of 2.73 in the very high category.

In this activity of utilizing environmental services, the forest farmer group manages a waterfall tourism village in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggaraong Seberang District.

d. Community Participation in the Utilization of Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs)

Community participation in the use of non-timber forest products in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggaraong Seberang District can be seen in Table 8.

Table 8. Community Participation in the Utilization of Non-Timber Forest Products in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	15	3	45
2	Sometimes	0	2	0
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		45
Average				3,00

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 8, it is known that all respondents often participate in the use of non-timber forest products because the use of non-timber forest products is an important activity in the management of non-timber forest products. The total score obtained was 45 with an average score of 3.00, which is in the very high category.

In non-timber forest product utilization activities, forest farmer group communities manage kelulut honey bees and make compost in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District.

e. Community Participation in Safeguarding and Preventing Forest and Land Fires

Community participation in securing and preventing forest and land fires in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Community Participation in Safeguarding and Preventing Forest and Land Fires in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Category	Number (Person)	Score	Total Score
1	Yes (Often)	5	3	15
2	Sometimes	10	2	20
3	Never	0	1	0
Total		15		35
Average				2,33

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 9, it is known that 5 respondents often participate in securing and preventing forest and land fires, and 10 respondents sometimes participate in securing and preventing forest and land fires. The total score obtained was 30 with an average score of 2.33 in the high category.

f. Recapitulation of Community Participation in Implementation

A recapitulation of community participation in the implementation of the Social Forestry program, which includes participation in planting, participation in maintenance, participation in the use of environmental services, participation in the use of non-timber forest products, participation in securing and preventing forest and land fires is presented in Table 10

Table 10. Recapitulation of Community Participation in the Implementation of Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

Questionnaire	Y/S (3)	NS	KK (2)	NS	T (1)	NS	Score Total	Average	
Planting	15	45	-	-	-	-	45	3,00	
Maintenance	13	39	2	4	-	-	43	2,87	
Utilization Environmental Services	12	36	2	4	1	1	41	2,73	
Utilization of Non- Timber Forest Products	15	45	-	-	-	-	45	3,00	
Security Area	5	15	10	20	-	-	35	2,33	
Amount								13,93	
Category								2,79	

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 10, shows Community Participation in the Implementation of the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District, the average scale score of 2.79 is in the very high category.

3. Level of Community Participation in Implementing Social Forestry Programs

The level of community participation in implementing the Social Forestry program is measured using a Likert scale, for details, see Table 11.

Table 11. Level of Community Participation in Implementing the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggara Seberang District

No	Type of Participation	Average Score
1	Preparation of RKUPS	2,40
2	Division of Work Plots	2,93
3	Training and development	3,00
4	Planting	3,00
5	Maintenance	2,87
6	Utilization of Environmental Services	2,73
7	Utilization of of non-timber forest products	3,00
8	Security and Prevention of Forest and Land Fires	2,33
Amount		22,26
Category		2,78

Source: Processed Data

Based on Table 11, shows that community participation in attending meetings for the preparation of social forestry business work plans is categorized as very high (average score of 2.40), community participation in the distribution of work plots is categorized as very high (average score of 2.93), community participation in training and development of forest farmer groups is very high (average score 3.00), community participation in planting is categorized as very high (average score

3.00), community participation in maintenance is categorized as very high (average score 2, 87), community participation in the utilization of environmental services is categorized as very high (average score 2.73), community participation in the utilization of non-timber forest products is categorized as very high (average score 3.00), and community participation in security and prevention Forest and land fires are categorized as high (average score 2.33).

Based on community participation from planning, training, and development to implementing activities, it can be concluded that the level of community participation in implementing the social forestry program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District with an average score of 2.78 is in the very high category. The research results are in line with the report of [8] that community empowerment activities around the forest in encouraging and increasing their participation are moving in a positive direction, even though it takes quite a long time. The benefits of social and economic empowerment through social forestry programs have been felt by village communities around the forest, resulting in changes in community attitudes and behavior in looting wood in the forest, as well as increasing participation in the program because of the demands of their living needs. The concepts of social institutions, capital, education and training, utilization of local resources, and mentoring have also been covered in the application of empowerment activities for village communities around the forest. The results of other research reported by [9] stated that community participation in forest management with the community in Bajulan Village was considered good as seen from community participation in decision-making, community participation in implementation includes the community's willingness to be involved during the bush clearing implementation process. harvesting pine sap, forest security, property participation by purchasing seeds independently by pesanggem (Forest Farmers); participation in taking benefits, and participation in evaluation. The results of this research contradict the report of [10] that community participation in the management of the Tandung Billa Community Forest (Hkm) is relatively low, which is caused by several factors, namely the lack of skills, experience, and opportunities for members in managing the Social Forestry Business Group.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded that the level of community participation in implementing the Social Forestry program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District is very high with an average score of 2.78.

B. Suggestions

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the author provides several suggestions for implementing the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District in the future, including:

1. The parties involved in the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village can maintain policy stability and produce innovations that strengthen the positive trend of the Social Forestry Program in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District so far.
2. Social Forestry Management in Bhuana Jaya Village, East Kalimantan needs to continue to be supported by implemented policies and programs to support the Social Forestry Program at the site level.
3. It is necessary to carry out further research either specifically or regarding other methods of approach to aspects of Social Forestry in Bhuana Jaya Village, Tenggarong Seberang District to provide suggestions for future strengthening.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Indonesian Ministry of Environment and Forestry. (2016). Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation No. 83 of 2016 concerning Social Forestry (p. 12).
- [2] Ministry of Environment and Forestry. 2021. Minister of Environment and Forestry Regulation No. 9 of 2021 concerning Social Forestry Management. Jakarta: Ministry of Environment and Forestry.
- [3] Supriyanto, B. 2019. Social Forestry policy innovation for fair management of natural resources and community welfare. Scientific Oration on the Anniversary of the USU Faculty of Forestry, Faculty of Forestry, University of North Sumatra, Medan.
- [4] Marschke M, Berkes F. 2005. Local level sustainability planning for livelihoods: A Cambodian experience. *International Journal of Sustainable Development and World Ecology* 12: 21-33.
- [5] Siahaya, M. E., Salampessy, M. L., Febryano, I. G., Rositah, E., Silamon, R. F., & Ichsan, A. C. (2016). Local community participation in mangrove forest conservation in the Tarakan region, North Kalimantan. *Nusa Sylva Journal*, 16(1), 12-17. Accessed on April 10 2022 from <https://www.ejournalunb.ac.id/index.php/JNS/article/view/181>
- [6] Laksemi, et al. 2019. Sustainable Social Forestry in Bali Province (Case Study in Wanagiri Village Forest). *Sustainable Social Forestry in Bali (A Case Study at Wanagiri Village Forest)*, 7(2) : 150-163.
- [7] Kusmayadi and E. Sugiarto. 2000. *Research Methods in the Field of Tourism*. PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, Jakarta.
- [8] Sumartono, D. Participation of Communities Around the Forest in Social Forestry Programs: Case Study in Kedung Salam Village, Donomulyo District, Malang Regency. UI Library, Jakarta. <Http://Lib.Ui.Ac.Id/Opac/Themes/Libri2/Detail.Jsp?Id=72024&Location=Lokal>
- [9] Evtasari, W.G. 2016. Community Participation in Joint Forest Management Programs Community in Bajulan Village, Loceret District, Nganjuk Regency. FISH State Administration Science Study Program, UNESA.
- [10] Witno, Maria, D. Supandi. 2020. Community Participation in Tandung Billa Community Forest Management (Hkm) in Battang Village, Palopo City. *Bonita Forestry Research Journal* 2 (2): 35-42